

New Data and Nomenclatural Notes on the Tephritidae (Diptera) of Far East Russia. I

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New Data and Nomenclatural Notes on the Tephritidae (Diptera) of Far East Russia. I. Korneyev V. A. — *Erectovena* Ito is resurrected from synonymy and shown to fit near *Dirioxa* Hendel rather than *Acanthonevra* Mcq. The following synonymy is established: *Soita* Walker, 1865 = *Phantasmia* Hendel, 1914, syn. n.; *Erectovena amurensis* (Portschinsky, 1892), comb. n. (= *Ptilona amurensis* Portsch.) = *Rioxoptilona speciosa* Hendel, 1915, syn. n.; *Acanthonevra pteropleuralis* (Hendel, 1927) = *A. melanostoma* (Hering, 1941), syn. n. The concept of several Palaearctic genera and new records of Adraminae and Dacinae in Far East Russia are discussed.

Нові дані та нотатки з номенклатури Tephritidae (Diptera) Далекого Сходу Росії. I. Корнеев В. О. — *Erectovena* Ito відновлено з синонімії; показано, що цей рід є ближчим до *Dirioxa* Hendel, ніж до *Acanthonevra* Mcq. Встановлено синоніми: *Soita* Walker, 1865 = *Phantasmia* Hendel, 1914, syn. n.; *Erectovena amurensis* (Portschinsky, 1892), comb. n. (= *Ptilona amurensis* Portsch.) = *Rioxoptilona speciosa* Hendel, 1915 syn. n.; *Acanthonevra pteropleuralis* (Hendel, 1927) = *A. melanostoma* (Hering, 1941), syn. n. Обговорюється систематичне положення і діагнози деяких палеарктичних родів і нові знахідки Adraminae та Dacinae на Далекому Сході Росії.

Новые данные и замечания по номенклатуре Tephritidae (Diptera) Дальнего Востока России. I. Корнеев В. А. *Erectovena* Ito восстановлена из синонимии; показано, что этот род ближе к *Dirioxa* Hendel, чем к *Acanthonevra* Mcq. Установлены синонимы: *Soita* Walker, 1865 = *Phantasmia* Hendel, 1914, syn. n.; *Erectovena amurensis* (Portschinsky, 1892), comb. n. (= *Ptilona amurensis* Portsch.) = *Rioxoptilona speciosa* Hendel, 1915 syn. n.; *Acanthonevra pteropleuralis* (Hendel, 1927) = *A. melanostoma* (Hering, 1941), syn. n. Обсуждаются систематическое положение и диагнозы ряда палеарктических родов и новые находки Adraminae и Dacinae на Дальнем Востоке России.

When preparing the tephritid chapter for the “Keys to Insects of Far East Russia” (Korneyev, Ovchinnikova, in prep.) several new synonyms and names that need to be resurrected from synonymy, and other previously unpublished nomenclatural changes were noted; new undescribed taxa were recognized, and some already known species and their host plants were recorded in Far East Russia for the first time.

An aim of this paper was to point out such improvements and additions to the Russian Far East fauna and to supply them with proper explanations and comments.

The type and other specimens are deposited in the following institutions:

Instytut Zoologiczny, Polska Akademia Nauk, Warszawa (IZPW); Natural History Museum, London (NHML), Naturhistorisches Museum Wien (NHMW), Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology, Kiev (SIZK), Természettudományi Múzeum Állattára, Budapest (TMB), Zoological Institute of Russian Academy of Sciences, Saint-Petersburg (ZISP), Zoological Museum of Moscow University (ZMUM).

Subfamilial and tribal position uncertain

Matsumurania sapporensis (Matsumura)

Korneyev, 1990.

While dissecting a female of this species, the 1st instar larvae were found in the female abdomen. It shows that this species apparently is could be viviparous, the feature rather common in some parasitoid Diptera, but not yet recorded for Tephritidae. Also, *M. sapporensis* has two rows of tiny postocular setae instead of single row of rather strong postoculars, as normally occurs in Tephritidae (except for Ortalotrypetini). Up to present, males are unknown.

Subfamily Phytalmiinae

Tribe Acanthonevrini

Erectovena Ito

Erectovena Ito, 1984 (type-species: *Rioxoptilona speciosa* Hendel, 1914), resurr. from synonymy. — *Acanthonevra* Macquart, *pro parte*: Hardy, 1986; Korneyev, 1990; 1994; Thompson et al., 1997.

Included species. By far, the single species, *Erectovena amurensis* (Portsch.), comb. n., should be included. The species that could be putatively placed here, *Rioxoptilona desperata* Hering, 1939, from Yunnan (China), Laos and Vietnam has long ventral rays of arista but no additional anepisternal bristle, and *Rioxoptilona trigonina* Zia, 1963, from Chekiang (China), has short ventral rays of arista and no additional anepisternal bristle, and fits near the concept of *Dirioxa*, indicating that *Erectovena* apparently could be synonymized in subsequent revisions of Acanthonevrini.

Synonymy of this generic name depends on the concept of the genus *Acanthonevra* s. l. The latter genus is mostly Oriental in distribution and has never been revised or properly proved to be a monophyletic taxon. Hardy (1986) took it largely, including also species assigned to *Rioxoptilona* Hendel and *Chaetomerella* de Meijere. Following that concept, *Erectovena* must be lumped together with *Acanthonevra*. For this reason Korneyev (1990) synonymized both names.

Recently, Permkam and Hancock (1995) completely re-arranged generic composition of Acanthonevrini, and considered some Australian species that generally fit Hardy's concept of *Acanthonevra* to belong to separate genera. In the key to Australian genera (Permkam, Hancock, 1995), Asian species assigned to *Lenitovena* run to *Dirioxa* Hendel, 1928.

Erectovena easily differs among Asian Acanthonevrini by the 2 fr, well-developed ventral row of rays on arista, straight R_{4+5} , supernumerary bristle at anteroventral margin of anepisternum and strong intercalary scutellar bristles, exceeding half of b sctl length. It differs from *Dirioxa* also by well-developed ventral row of rays on arista.

Erectovena amurensis (Portschinsky), comb. n.

amurensis Portschinsky, 1892 (*Ptilona*); Hendel, 1927; Korneyev, 1990; Thompson et al., 1997 (*Acanthonevra*). — *speciosa* Hendel, 1915; Shiraki, 1933; Chen, 1948; Zia, 1963 (*Rioxoptilona*); Hardy, 1977; 1986; Korneyev, 1990; Thompson et al., 1997 (*Acanthonevra*); Ito, 1984; 1986; Kwon, 1985; Ito, Tamaki, 1994 (*Erectovena*), syn. n.

Material. Lectotype *P. amurensis*: ♀: “*Ptilona amurensis*”, Russia: “Amur, Wladiwostok” (ZISP) (examined and designated by inference of holotype, see: Korneyev, 1990). Holotype *Rioxoptilona speciosa*: ♂: [“Hoozan, Janner, Deutsch. Ent. Mus.”] not found neither in DEI (Rohlfien, Ewald, 1970) nor in NHMW, and is probably lost.

Though the holotype of *R. speciosa* could not be located, its original description is informative and includes the most essential characters like the pattern of the mesonotal scutum and the abdomen, and the presence of the supernumerary bristle on the anepisternum. These characters fit well both the lectotype of *P. amurensis* and the Japanese specimens of *E. speciosa* (the latter described and figured by Ito). This allows to consider both names as synonyms.

Chaetomerella de Meijere

Chaetomerella de Meijere, 1914 (type-species: *Chaetomerella nigrifacies* de Meijere, 1914).

This genus first was synonymized with *Phorelliosoma* by Hendel (1915; 1927), that subsequently was not accepted by Chen (1948) and Ito (1984). They used the generic name *Chaetomerella* de Meijere for the single species, *Ch. varipes* Chen from Kyusyu, Sikoku and Taiwan, but none of them compared that species with the type species of *Chaetomerella*. Hardy (1986 b) considered *Chaetomerella nigrifacies* (known from the holotype female) as a synonym of *Acanthonevra lieflincki* Hering that was collected in the same type locality on Java and has similar wing pattern, but differs by the undulate R_{2+3} , arista long pubescent and both prst sa and prsc ac well-developed. Hardy writes that he had only the photograph of *Ch. nigrifacies* holotype when redescribing the species and insists that the arista rays and the lacking bristles could be merely rubbed off, and the R_{2+3} nearly straight could be an aberrant character state. This explanation hardly could be accepted taking into consideration that each of these characters occurs elsewhere in Acanthonevrini. For this reason I consider identity of both *Ch. nigrifacies* and the genus *Chaetomerella* to be uncertain, and prefer to use the generic name *Orienticaelum* Ito until the concept of *Ch. nigrifacies* would be clarified.

Orienticaelum Ito

Orienticaelum Ito, 1984 (type-species: *Rioxoptilona femorata* Shiraki, 1933).

The type species of this genus and “*Chaetomerella*” *varipes* Chen share reduced chaetotaxy of mesonotum (no prst and prsc), straight R_{2+3} and 2 fr + 2 or and shortly pubescent arista. *Ptilona* Wulp clearly differs from them by 1 fr + 1 or, long plumose arista and long black pubescence on katatergum. As the concept of the genus *Chaetomerella* was never explicitly defined, we consider all its possible synonyms separately. For these reasons,

"*Chaetomerella*" *varipes* is keyed under *Orienticaelum* (Korneyev, Ovchinnikova, in preparation), but formally its original combination is retained.

Phorelliosoma Hendel, and its type species, *Ph. hexachaeta* Hendel, from Taiwan is another acanthonevrine with 2 or, 2 fr bristles, short rays of arista, no ipa, and rather short i sclt ($< 2/5$ b sclt). It certainly differs from the species here assigned to *Orienticaelum* by completely developed prst, prsc and dc. *Mimosophira rubra* Hardy from Vietnam fits near *Ph. hexachaeta* in the wing shape and pattern, and in the chaetotaxy, except for anterior or and kept in *M. rubra* lacking, and mesonotum with no black spots. These two species apparently are closely related.

Acanthonevra Macquart

Acanthonevra Macquart, 1843 (type-species: *Acanthonevra fuscipennis* Macquart, 1843); Hardy, 1977; 1986; Korneyev, 1990; 1994; Thompson et al., 1997. — *Lenitovena* Ito, 1984.

Comparing to my previous works (Korneyev, 1990; 1994), the concept of the Palaearctic *Acanthonevra* is somewhat restricted herein. The species Ito assigned to *Lenitovena* Ito and *A. fuscipennis* share quite enough key characters to be considered as congeneric. These are as follows: arista rather long pubescent both dorsally and ventrally; 1 fr + 2 or; mesonotum with full set of bristles; no "intrapostalars"; i sclt shorter than $1/3$ of b sclt; R_{2+3} undulate; t_2 with 1 spur; phallapodema with partially separate vanes; surstyli rather long and broad; spermathecae hemispheric, mushroom-like without nipples. The only essential difference is that *A. trigona* Mats., *A. formosana* End., *A. amamioshimensis* Shiraki as well as some other species have both the fore femur with abundance of black setae on antero- and postero-ventral surfaces and front tibia densely black setose while *A. fuscipennis* has neither femur nor tibia ornate in both sexes. This character is only of infrageneric importance.

Acanthonevra pteropleuralis (Hendel)

pteropleuralis Hendel, 1927 (*Acanthonevra*); Korneyev, 1990; Thompson et al., 1997 (*Acanthonevra*); Ito, 1984; Kwon, 1985; Ito, Tamaki, 1994 (*Lenitovena*). — *melanostoma* Hering, 1941 (*Acanthonevra*); Ito, 1984; Korneyev, 1990; Thompson et al., 1997 (*Acanthonevra*), **syn. n.** — *formosana* Enderlein, 1911; Shiraki, 1933; Chen, 1948; Zia, 1963 (*Acanthonevra*); Hardy, 1973; 1977; 1986; Korneyev, 1990; Thompson et al., 1997 (*Acanthonevra*), **unconfirmed senior synonymy.**

Material. Syntypes *P. pteropleuralis*: ♂♀: RUSSIA: "Amur" (not located) (not found in NHMW). Holotype *A. melanostoma*: ♂: Northern China: "Heilongjiang, Maershan (MNHL) (examined). Holotype *Acanthonevra formosana*: ♀: ["Kosempo"] (IZPW) (not examined). Russia: several locations in Primorskiy Krai and Kurile Islands (see Korneyev, 1990); China: Taiwan: ♀: "Formosa Sauter, Ins. Lambeh, 1908 II", "*formosana* End. [Hendel det.] (NHMW).

Hardy (1973) synonymized *Acanthonevra pteropleuralis* with *A. formosana* Enderlein, as he "was unable to find any characters which seem to be reliable for differentiating these". Indeed, no reliable difference could be found between the female from Taiwan (NHMW) and the original description of Enderlein. In addition, the females from Amur and Japan are also

very similar. Nevertheless the males from Amur has the epandrium and surstyli much narrow and long than in the specimen figured by Hardy (1973: fig. 35 f). This indicates that there are at least 2 superficially similar species in South East Asia that differ in the structure of genitalia. Until the synonymy of *A. formosana* and *A. pteropleuralis* is resolved in a proper way, I prefer to consider them as separate species.

The holotype of *A. melanostoma* is merely a melanistic specimen conspecific with yellow-headed specimens of *A. pteropleuralis* (from Primorskiy Krai) that have same structure of male genitalia.

Subfamily Adraminae ?

Soita Walker

Soita Walker, 1865 (type-species: *Soita psiloides* Walker, 1865). — *Phantasmia* Hendel, 1914, *syn. n* (type-species: *Phantasmia cylindrica* Hendel, 1914).

The type species of *Phantasmia* is very close or identical to *Soita baltazarae* Hardy, and the two generic names are certainly synonyms. Tribal placement of this genus is doubtful. The arrangement of fronto-orbital and scutellar bristles, structure of male and female genitalia are rather similar to those in *Microneurina* Permkam & Hancock, another genus of uncertain position that shows no adramine appearance. The only character that *Soita* shares with Adramini, long setulose katatergum has been shown to be the subject of convergence in Adraminae, on one hand, and *Ptilona* (Acanthonevrini), on the other (Korneyev, 1994).

Soita cylindrica (Hendel), *comb. n.*

cylindrica Hendel, 1914; 1915; Thompson et al., 1997 (*Phantasmia*). — Ito, Tamaki, 1995 (*Soita* sp.). — *baltazarae* Hardy, 1974; Thompson et al., 1997 (*Soita*), possible, but unconfirmed junior synonymy.

Material. Syntype *P. cylindrica*: ♂ (abdomen lost): China (Taiwan): “Kankau (Form.) H. Sauter IX. 12”, “Cotype ♂” [red paper], “*Phantasmia cylindrica* det. Hendel”, “Coll. Hendel”, “Cotype ♂, Marked by D. E. Hardy — 1961” (NHMW).

Ito and Tamaki (1995) have recently recorded an undetermined species of this genus from the Palearctic Japan, and the specimen they mentioned very probably belongs to *S. cylindrica*, known by far from Taiwan. The type specimens (♂♂) of *Phantasmia cylindrica* from Taiwan and the holotype ♀ of *Soita baltazarae* from the Philippines share same wing pattern and the abdomen similarly marked with black, that suggests they may be conspecific. But their synonymization is still pending until more material is available.

Subfamily Adraminae

All the species of this tribe known for the Russian Far East except the following one were reviewed by Korneyev (1990).

Rhacochlaena transmontana (Ito)

Ito, 1984.

Material. Southern Sakhalin: Tshekhov mountain, h=500 m, 28.06.1988, ♀ (Nesterov) (SIZK) (new for Russia).

Discussion. This species fits very near to European *Rh. toxoneura* Lw., and also is an inquiline in the *Pontania* sawfly galls (A. G. Zinovjev, unpublished data). Apparently it is to be treated better as a subspecies of the former species.

Subfamily Dacinae

Tribe Gastrozonini

Only *Paragastrozona japonica* Shiraki was recorded up today (Richter, 1963).

Acrotaeniostola scutellaris (Matsumura)

Matsumura, 1916 (*Trypeta*); Ito, 1984.

Material. Southern Kurils: Kunashir, caldera of the Golovnin Volcano, Goriacheie Lake, 16.08.1988, ♂ (Kotenko) (SIZK) (new for Russia).

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References

- Chen S. H. [1948]. Notes on Chinese Trypetinae. — *Sinensia*, 1947, 18: 69–123.
- Enderlein G. 1911. Trypetiden-Studien. — *Zool. Jahrb. Abt. syst. geogr. biol. Tiere*. 31: 407–416.
- Foote R. H. 1984. Family Tephritidae (Trypetidae). In: Soós Á., Papp L., eds. *Catalogue of Palaearctic Diptera. Vol. 9. Micropezidae — Agromyzidae*. Budapest, Akadémiai Kiadó: 66–149.
- Hardy D. E. 1973. The fruit flies (Tephritidae —Diptera) of Thailand and bordering countries. — *Pac. Insects Monogr.* 31: 353 p.
- Hardy D. E. 1974. The fruit flies of the Philippines (Diptera: Tephritidae). — *Pac. Insects Monogr.* 32: 266 p.
- Hardy D. E. 1977. Family Tephritidae (Trypetidae, Trypaneidae). In: Delfinado M. D., Hardy D. E., eds. *A Catalog of the Diptera of the Oriental Region. Volume III. Suborder Cyclorrhapha (excluding subdivision Aschiza)*. Honolulu, University of Hawaii Press: 44–134.
- Hardy D. E. 1986. Fruit flies of the subtribe Acanthonevrina of Indonesia, New Guinea, and the Bismarck and Solomon islands (Diptera: Tephritidae: Trypetinae: Acanthonevrini). — *Pac. Insects Monogr.* 42: 191 p.
- Hendel F. 1914. Die Gattungen der Bohrfliegen. (Analytische Übersicht aller bisher bekannten Gattungen der Tephritinae.). — *Wien. entomol. Ztg.* 33: 73–98.
- Hendel F. 1927. 49. Trypetidae. In: Lindner E., Ed. *Die Fliegen der paläarktischen Region*. Stuttgart, E. Schweizerbart. Verl. (Erwin Nägele): 5 (Lfg. 16–19): 221 S.

- Hendel F. 1915. H. Sauter's Formosa-Ausbeute. Tephritinae. — *Ann. Hist. Nat. Mus. Natnl. Hung.* 13: 424–467.
- Hering E. M. 1941. Neue Dacinae und Trypetinae des Zoologischen Museums der Universität Berlin. — *Siruna Seva.* 3: 1–25.
- Ito S. 1984. *Die japanischen Bohrfliegen*. Osaka: Selbstverlag S. Ito. [Maruzen Co., Ltd.] (Lfg.2): 49–96.
- Ito S. 1986. Fruitflies in Niigata Prefecture (Diptera: Tephritidae). — [*Trans. Essa Entomol. Soc. Niigata*]. 62:21–27. (In Japanese).
- Ito S., Tamaki N. 1995. Fruitflies caught in fluorescent light trap on Mt. Akagi, Central Honshu, Japan (2). — *Yosegaki.* 74: 1787–1790. (In Japanese).
- Korneyev V. A. [1990]. A review of Sphenella and Paroxyyna series of genera (Diptera, Tephritidae, Tephritinae) of Eastern Palaearctic. — *Nasekomye Mongolii.* Leningrad, Nauka: 1989, 11: 395–470. (In Russian; English summary).
- Korneyev V. A. 1994. Reclassification of Palaearctic Tephritidae (Diptera). Communication 2. — *Vestn. Zool.* (1): 3–17. (In Russian; English summary).
- Kwon Y. J. 1985. Classification of the fruitfly-pests from Korea. — *Insecta Koreana Series* 5: 49–112.
- Matsumura S. [Thousand insects of Japan. Additamenta]. — *Thousand insects of Japan.* Vol. 2. Tokyo, [Keisei-sha]: 413–424.
- Permkam S., Hancock D. L. 1995. Australian Trypetinae (Diptera: Tephritidae). — *Invertebrate Taxonomy.* 9: 1047–1209.
- Portschinsky I. A. 1892. Diptera europaea et asiatica nova aut minus cognita. — *Horae Soc. Entomol. Ross.* 26: 201–227.
- Richter V. A. 1963. A report on the fruit-flies (Diptera, Trypetidae) of the Soviet Far East. — *Zool. Zhurn.* 42: 770–772. (In Russian; English summary).
- Rohlfien K., Ewald B. 1970. Katalog der in dem Sammlungen des ehemaligen Deutschen Entomologischen Institutes aufbewahrten Typen — VIII. — *Beitr. Ent.* 22(7/8): 407 - 469.
- Shiraki T. 1933. A systematic study of Trypetidae in the Japanese Empire. — *Mem. Fac. Sci. Agric., Taihoku Imp. Univ.* 8(Entomol. 2): 509 p.
- Thompson F. C., Norrbom A. L., Carroll L. E., Freidberg A., White I. M. 1997. *Fruit Fly BioSystematic Information Database and Expert System*. — Washington.
- Zia Y. 1963. Notes on Chinese trypetid flies II. — *Acta Entomol. Sin.* 12: 631–648.